

Somesy: Software Metadata Synchronyzation

Orchestrating Metadata Harmony for Pioneering Research Software

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Abstract

In the diverse landscape of research software, maintaining consistent and accurate metadata across configuration files such as CITATION.cff, codemeta.json, pyproject.toml, package.json, and more, is time-consuming and error-prone. As a result, metadata of many software projects is inconsistent, incomplete or simply lacking.

Somesy addresses this problem: it is a command-line tool crafted to automate the synchronization of research software project metadata across various file formats. By centralizing metadata in a single configuration file, Somesy ensures that important project details, including version, authorship, licenses, and repository links, are consistently updated across all associated outputs. This enhances the overall quality and reproducibility and FAIRness of the code.

By incorporating user feedback, user-requested features and dynamically updating the tool to resolve reported issues, our team ensures Somesy remains a robust, user-friendly, and cross-platform solution. This commitment to active maintenance and iterative improvement guarantees that Somesy not only meets current metadata management needs but is also well-prepared to adapt to future challenges in the research software community.

Keywords: FAIR, Metadata, Software, RSD, Software Metadata

Resources

The material and resources (e.g. data, model, codes, documentation, videos) which underly, support or are closely related to your contribution deposited on a repository, please include a title, the respective DOI(s) and brief description. E.g.

- GitHub page: <https://github.com/Materials-Data-Science-and-Informatics/somesy> "Software Metadata Synchronizing."
- Somesy in Helmholtz RSD: <https://helmholtz.software/software/somesy>

Author contributions

Conceptualization: MS, VH; Data Curation: MS; Funding acquisition: VH, SS; Methodology: MS; Project administration: VH; Resources: VH, SS; Software: MS; Supervision: VH, SS; Writing-original draft: MS, VH; Writing – review & editing: SS, MS, VH.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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